

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2
0
2
4

No 7

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

*Elektron nashr. 70 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 4-iyulda ruxsat etildi.*

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti rektori
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, p.f.f.d., (PhD), Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Hududiy ta'lim muassasalari va markazlar bo'yicha prorektor v.b.
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d., TSUE professori
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Cham Tat Huei, (PhD) USCI universiteti professori, Malayziya
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d.,(PhD) "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d.,(PhD) TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Djudi Smetana, p.f.n., Pittsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Krissi Lyuis, p.f.n., Pittsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Ali Kopak (Али Кўнак), i.f.d., prof., Karabuk universiteti dosenti, Turkiya
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, i.f.n., "LUKOIL-Energoservis" Kompaniyasi iqtisodchisi, Moskva.
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., (PhD) TDIU dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Oqil Umurzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjaevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Rae Kwon Chung, honorary professor of TSUE, Nobel laureate, South Korea,

Osman Mesten, member of the Turkish Parliament, head of the Turkey-Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, DSc, Prof., Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Buzrukkhanov Sarvarkhan Munavvarkhanovich, DSc, Deputy Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, DSc, Prof., Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich CSc, Prof., Rector of Academy of Labor and Social Relations

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, DSc, Prof., TSUE Vice-Rector for Scientific Affairs and Innovation

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhriddinovich, DSc, Prof., Rector of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Siddikova Sadokat Ghaforovna, PhD, Rector of the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, DSc, Prof., acting Vice-rector for regional educational institutions and centers of TSUE

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, CSc, Prof., of TSUE

Slizovsky Dimitriy Yegorovich, DSc, Prof., of the People's Friendship University of Russia

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, DSc, Prof., Rector of International "Nordic" University

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, PhD, professor of TDIU

Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja ugli, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of the DGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the DCECGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganievich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Shoira Azimovna Musaeva, professor of SamDu IS Institute

Cham Tat Huei, PhD, professor at USCI University, Malaysia

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, PhD, deputy of executive director of the "El-yurt umidi" fund

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, PhD, Senior Lecturer at Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

Judy Smetana CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Chrissy Lewis CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Ali Konak DSc, Prof., Associate Professor of Karabuk University, Turkey

Glazova Marina Viktorovna, CSc, economist at LUKOIL-Energoservis Company, Moscow.

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, associate professor of TSUE

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, doctoral student at Ankara University, Turkey

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, independent researcher of TSUE

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, p.f.f.d., (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Avtosanoat korxonalari marketing strategiyasini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	16
Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, Zayniddinova Umida Djalolovna	
Mamlakat raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda maxsus iqtisodiy zonalar omilidan foydalanish istiqbollari	26
Izbosarov Boburjon Baxriddinovich, Abdurasulov Ravshanbek Xotam o'g'li	
Mahalla institutini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning institutsional tahlili	32
Bahriddinov Viqorjon Akbar o'g'li	
Mamlakatimizda pillachilik biznesini rivojlantirish orqali mahsulot ishlab chiqarish va uni qayta ishlash holatining tahlili	37
Turgunov Odilbek Maripovich	
Etnografik turizmni tashkil etishning xorij tajribasi	41
I. Axmedov	
Xizmatlar sohasining milliy iqtisodiyotdagi rolini tahlil qilishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari.....	46
Xusanov Murodjon Sunnatullayevich	
Iqtisodiy o'sish tushunchasi va uning rivojlanish tarixi.....	54
Maksudov Avazbek Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jarayonlarni takomillashtirish asosida inson kapitalini rivojlantirish	59
Ubaydullaev G'ayrat Zuvaytovich	
O'zbekistonda aholi bandligini ta'minlashda oilaviy tadbirkorlikning o'rni	65
Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna	
The Effect of Students' Financial Status on Academic Performance in Uzbekistan	70
Alimov Damirjon Odilovich	
Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida tadbirkorlik faoliyatining o'rni.....	76
Jusupova Anjim Tansiqbaevna	
Insurance Mechanisms in Foreign Trade: Mitigating Risk and Facilitating Global Commerce	82
Sohibjamol Abirkulova	
Nodavlat umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabning faoliyati samaradorligini aniqlashda innovatsion usullardan foydalanish.....	87
Ustadjalilova Xurshida Aliyevna	
Qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarida asosiy vositalar hisobi va auditi bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar va ulardan respublikamizda foydalanish imkoniyatlari	92
Xojimurodov Zuxriddin Shukurullo o'g'li	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi budjetining shakllanishida egri soliqlarni undirishning fiskal samaradorligi	97
Abdulxayeva Shahnoza Muxammadiyevna	
Mamlakat sanoatining barqaror rivojlanishida energosamaradorlikning roli	104
J. J. Yaxshilikov	
Сравнительный анализ состояния сферы услуг в регионах Андижанской области	109
Мусабоев Рустам Алижонович	
Hududlarda aholi bandligini oshirish va kambag'allikni qisqartirishda ishlab chiqarish sanoatining o'rni (Qashqadaryo viloyati misolida).....	114
Hamdamov Shahzod Ilhom o'g'li, Baxronov Baxriddin Najmiddinovich	

Banklarning qimmatli qog'ozlar bozoridaqi faoliyatini takomilashtirish yo'llari.....	118
Ermatov Utkirbek Baxodirjonovich	
Развитие цифровой экономики в Узбекистане, ее плюсы и минусы	122
Раупова Мухлисахон Ибрахимжон кизи, Мамбетова Мадина Зоҳид кизи, Алижонова Малика Алижон кизи, Хакимова Нигора Бахтиёрвна	
Investment Management is an Important Factor of Economic Development.....	127
Yuldasheva G. A., Ziyayev Dilshodjon	
O'zbekistonda moliyaviy texnologiyalar sanoatining rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	130
Rustamov Jasurbek Ravshanbek o'g'li	

INVESTMENT MANAGEMENT IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

UDK: 330322

Yuldasheva G. A.

Lecturer, Ferghana State University

Ziyayev Dilshodjon

Lecturer, Ferghana State University

Abstract: This article is devoted to the issue of the role of investment in the economy. The author considers the economic essence, significance, dynamics of investments, investment management, state support for foreign investments.

Key words: investments, capital raising, profitability, own capital, investment policy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola investitsiyalarning iqtisodiyotdagi o'rnini mavzusiga bag'ishlangan. Muallif tomonidan investitsiyalarning iqtisodiy mohiyati, ahamiyati, dinamikasi, investitsiyalarni boshqarish, xorijiy investitsiyalarni davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash masalalari o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: investitsiyalar, kapital jalb qilish, rentabellik, xususiy kapital, investitsiya siyosati.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы управления инвестициями в торговых предприятиях как фактор экономического развития. Данная статья посвящена вопросу роли инвестиций в экономике. Автор рассматривает экономическую сущность, значимость, динамику инвестиций, управление инвестициями.

Ключевые слова: инвестиции, привлечение капитала, рентабельность, собственный капитал, инвестиционная политика.

INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of the market economy, investments have become more important, since their decision depends on the success of the country in world competition, as well as on the success of its decision. Fixed capital investments determine economic efficiency and are the basis for the modernization of the economy. In order to maintain high rates of economic development, one of the main tasks of the state is to increase investments. Even under the most favorable circumstances, the company's own funds are limited to the amount of current income and depreciation. If the return on investment is higher than the cost of raising capital, then it is rational to borrow funds from external sources.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issues of the interconnectedness of investment and economic growth is revealed in the studies of R. Alvarado (2017), D. Burns, A. Jones, T. Gao (2005), Y. Goryakin, A. Kumar Tiwari (2011), T. Kunieda (2016), M. Suhrcke (2017), G. Kharlamova (2014), Z. Varnalii (2018), D. Nikytenko (2018), etc. Numerous studies of well-known economists from all over the world are devoted to the problem of building a system of economic growth factors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the article, analytical data were used in the research conducted by the author. The subject is covered through practical skills.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The coronavirus pandemic has greatly affected the global flow of foreign direct investment. In 2020, they rose by a third, to \$1 trillion, well below the level seen after the global crisis a decade ago. How the international investment flow is vital for sustainable development in the poor countries of the world.

The global investment process has slowed down, and prospects for reducing investment have forced businesses to rethink new projects.

Attracting foreign investment to developing countries decreased by more than 8 percent, mainly due to the stability of their flow in Asia. As a result, 2/3% of the global direct investment in the share of developing countries was more than half that of 2022. Investments in new enterprises in developed countries decreased by 42%, international agreements on financing important infrastructure projects decreased by 14%, international agreements on financing infrastructure projects decreased by 14%, and financing of international projects decreased by 19%. projects increased by 8%. The overall decrease in new project activity, combined with a decrease in international investment, led to a more than 50% decrease in investment in stock capital. Different levels of the national economic system played an important role in the overall management of economic processes. Investment management can be considered at different levels depending on investment goals and opportunities. If investment activities are carried out at the federal level, investment management is carried out at the state level, regulation, promotion and control of investment activities are carried out by both regulatory and legislative methods.

Management of investment relations within the framework of the implementation of an investment project of a particular enterprise includes the development of a business plan, further control over the subsequent investment process.

Investment management at the level of an economic entity is a set of principles and methods of performing management tasks included in the basis of all investment activities of the company. A properly planned process of managing investment relations in an enterprise usually leads to increased competitiveness and economic growth in a dynamic economic environment.

The main goal of investment management is to implement effective forms of investment to ensure high development rates, expand economic and financial potential, and ensure financial stability. In other words, the ultimate goal of investment management is to develop a clear investment plan. Investment policy is a set of measures taken by the state to control investment activity in order to create optimal conditions for improving the investment process. As part of the investment strategy of the enterprise, a special plan for the implementation of investment activities has been developed in order to increase the efficiency of investment activities. The real investment policy is a part of the general investment plan of the enterprise, which ensures the preparation, examination and implementation of the most effective real investment project.

In the conditions of high investment activity of the enterprise, the investment management policy consists in developing a real investment management strategy together with the financing strategy, which should ensure the optimal amount of value and capital structure in general. The fact is that various investment cluster approaches to the implementation of the enterprise's investment strategy, including real investment management policy, have a special place in this process. Investment policy is an integral part of state economic policy. Investing creates problems not only for the investor, but also for the investor. Thus, by solving problems and eliminating fluctuations, the investor can make significant progress towards achieving his goal - obtaining investment funds. The active influence of the state on investment processes is a necessary condition for a favorable investment environment and revitalization of investment activities, which ensures a stable economic system for the benefit of all people. Administrative, economic and administrative means of influencing the investment process are used in the direct regulation of investment activity by the state. When using administrative means, the state directly affects the investment process based on binding decisions. Such tools can be called state registration of business entities, licensing, setting export and import quotas, control of state enterprises and state property, administrative procedures, etc. A direct effect of economic impact is investing in certain regions, sectors and enterprises that cannot withstand strong competition in the market due to the nature of their activity. For example, sectors of the economy that require knowledge have a high investment risk, the investment process takes place from time to time, projects are considered long-term and expensive. The main problem for an investor is to get complete information, because it is complete should receive information. decide where, in what form, for how long and safely to invest. In order to obtain such quality information, it is necessary to conduct a careful study, which should be used to select the object and apply the best method of its evaluation.

CONCLUSION

Two of the most important conditions for effective accumulation in the modernization process must be met: the protection of property rights, as well as macroeconomic stability. But the investment process is carried out in full only after the entire system is formed. market incentives for capital growth at the micro level: increasing company value. Firms can adapt to some kind of incentive system, often referred to as the investment climate, but often associated with risks, hazards, and losses. Its specificity determines the changes in the direction and intensity of accumulation by industry, region and business type. The investment environment may be in line with other business sectors and may not be in line with the country's expectations, such as government plans and economic modernization. Ensuring a high level of investment actually means expanding its use.

Literature:

1. Yuldasheva, GA, & Khamidov, K. (2022). Processes of modernization of the accounting system at enterprises. *Gospodarka i Innovatsije.*, 30, 230-231.
2. Yuldasheva, GA (2022). The significance of innovative experience in forming an increase in the level of income of the population. *Devotees of Education*, 8, 172-185.
3. Yuldasheva, G., & Kuchkarova, A. (2020). Investment in the development of the regions and the specific characteristics of their management. in financial-legal and innovation aspects of regional economy investment (pp. 543-547).
4. Yuldasheva, GA, & Toirjonov, J. (2022). Development of social infrastructure-development of the region. *Gospodarka i Innovatsije.*, 29, 149-154.
5. Achilov, AN (2018). Taking into account the consumption of commodity reserves in the chemical industry in our country and issues of its improvement. *Economics and Finance (Uzbekistan)*, (8), 54-58.
6. Хомидов, К. К. (2019). Socioeconomic characteristics of employment in Uzbekistan. *Инновационная наука*, (7-8), 64-66.
7. Хомидов, К. К. (2019). Перспективный комплекс экономики Узбекистана. In *Современная мировая экономика: проблемы и перспективы в эпоху развития цифровых технологий и биотехнологии* (pp. 54-56).
8. Homidov, K. (2023). Conceptual approaches to the formation of a model for the sustainable development of tourist complexes. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 2(7), 33-38.
9. Homidov, K. (2023). Organizational and economic foundations of the organization of tourist complexes in the development of tourism in the regions. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(7), 44-50.
10. Homidov Kakhkhorali Kurbonali ugli. (2023). Objective need for the formation and sustainable development of tourist complexes in the regions: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8151902>. *IQRO* , 4(2), 42–45.
11. Хомидов, К. (2023). O'zbekistonda turistik majmualar faoliyatini boshqaruv samaradorligi oshirish yo 'llari. *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 11(3), 154-160.
12. Xomidov, X. (2023). Hududlarda turistik majmualar faoliyatini shakillantirish va tizimli boshqarish asosida hududlar turistik salohiyatidan samarali foydalanish masalalari. " Milliy iqtisodiyotni isloh qilish va barqaror rivojlantirish istiqbollari" respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari to 'plami., 412-415.
13. Хомидов, Қ.Қ.Ў.(2023). Организационно-экономический механизм развития туристических комплексов. In *Новые технологии в учебном процессе и производстве* (pp. 370-372).
14. Хомидов, Қ. Қ. (2023). Инновационные преимущества использования информационных технологий в туристической деятельности. In *современные вопросы естествознания и экономики* (pp. 421-424).6. Сафарова, Д. (2023). Использование информационных технологий для развития цифровой экономики и области статистики в республике. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(5), 171-177.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtjmoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. № 7

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

